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DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNITY BUILDING REPORT V2

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Abstract	The document reports about stakeholder engagement, dissemination and communication activities during the entire duration of the ACTION project and monitors their success. It also provides the strategy on the legacy of ACTION outputs.
Keywords	Dissemination and communication activities, monitoring of outreach, legacy

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the achievements of the ACTION communication, dissemination and networking activities for the entire duration of the project (from 1 February 2019 until end of January 2022). It covers the analysis of all channels used, both online and offline. This includes the project website, the social media channels, the newsletter, the realised videos, printed materials, the final conference, presentations at events through talks and posters, scientific publications, networking activities with other projects and the citizen science community.

It also shows the performance of communication and dissemination activities towards the KPIs defined in the Description of Action (DoA). Most KPIs were achieved, some by large. Due to the fact that communication and dissemination was implemented mainly online due to the COVID19 pandemic, some KPIs were not as relevant as at the beginning of the project and therefore have not been completely reached. Instead, online activities were strengthened.

With this report, the reader gets an overview on the variety of implemented activities that should ensure the visibility of the ACTION project and that it became an important player in the citizen science community in Europe.

The report is an extension of the Dissemination and community building report v1 (D7.2), focusing on the activities for the period May 2020 - January 2022. It is closely linked to the sustainability plan v2 (D7.5), in particular to the legacy of the ACTION outputs.

1 INTRODUCTION

This report presents the achievements of the ACTION communication, dissemination and networking activities for the entire duration of the project (from 1 February 2019 until end of January 2022).

It presents the activities and the results of the implementation of the dissemination and engagement plan (D7.1, with the updated version as Annex in D7.2) by analysing the outreach of the channels and tools that the project used to reach the target groups defined in D7.1. It also presents the achievements towards the Key Performance Indicators. All this allows an evaluation of the communication, dissemination and networking activities and related learnings for the whole duration of ACTION.

This document also informs about the legacy of the project website. Therefore it is closely linked to the sustainability plan v2 (D7.5) where specific strategies for the most important project outputs are described in detail.

The document is the third deliverable of WP 7 “Stakeholders engagement, dissemination and sustainability” and especially of Task 7.2 “Dissemination and communication” which aimed to define and oversee the dissemination and communication strategy and to help in aligning and exploring synergies between different outreach-related activities in WPs 2 to 6.

The report is also providing further details on the WP7 activities description in the second official progress report.

Remark: in various chapters of this report we provide numbers about how many people we reached with our ACTION dissemination activities (e.g. at events or through online communication), in some parts by target groups. We would like to point out that in many cases it was not possible to obtain neither the exact number of recipients or participants, nor the target group to which participants belonged to. In particular this refers to online events and online dissemination that were not organised or published by the consortium partners. Therefore the numbers that we present here are a conservative calculation.

2 DIFFERENT PHASES OF DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION AND NETWORKING DURING THE ACTION PROJECT LIFETIME

The dissemination, communication and networking (community building) of ACTION followed different phases which accompanied the implementation of project activities in the other work packages:

In the first six months the project consortium laid the foundation for starting to disseminate the project to the outside world by defining the dissemination and community building strategy, developing the branding, setting up the most important online channels (project website and social media accounts), realising project materials and templates and establishing contact and collaboration agreements with the sister projects, and in particular with the coordination action EU-Citizen.Science.

In the next phase (months 6 to 9) project activities started and focused on the promotion of the 1st Open Call¹ (including information about the project). For this, a promotion pack was created, including a postcard both in electronic and paper form, a banner, two short videos, an email format to be used by all the partners for promoting the call through their contacts, Twitter and Facebook post templates again to be used by project partners following an agreed calendar for posting, a standard presentation presenting the project, the call and the submission procedure and a dedicated dissemination strategy for the Open Call in particular with internal deadlines and the division of work among project partners. This led to an intensive promotion through the project website, the ACTION social media channels, the newsletter and through networking activities of all partners in their communities, both online and via face to face events. A paid advertisement campaign was also carried out on Facebook in order to support the Call-related information to reach new contacts at EU level. In addition, dissemination activities both on the level of the ACTION pilots as well on the general project started, reporting on first activities and results.

During a third phase (months 9 to 21) the ACTION pilots from the 1st Open Call round were presented and promoted (e.g. together with the Accelerator kick-off meeting in Berlin in February 2020 or regular news on the ACTION online tools). The project website further developed (also taking into account comments of the first external review), by presenting the ACTION pilots in a more prominent way, providing more information on the Accelerator programme, adding the toolkit and masterclass pages as well as structuring the access to the ACTION Resources. A highlight in this phase was the [ACTION Lab](#) during the Ars Electronica festival 2020 in which 6 ACTION pilots were presented.

Beginning in the third phase, the fourth phase (months 19 to 21) promoted the 2nd Open Call (published through a [dedicated page](#) on the ACTION website). Similar to the 1st Open Call, a promotion pack was created, including a press release, a postcard in electronic form, a banner, two short videos, an email format to be used by all consortium partners for promoting the call through their contacts, Twitter and Facebook post templates again to be used by project partners following an agreed calendar for posting, a standard PPT presentation presenting the project, the call and the submission procedure and a dedicated dissemination strategy for the Open Call in particular with internal deadlines and the division of work among project partners. As for the 1st Open Call, this led to an intensive promotion through the project website, the ACTION social media channels, the newsletter and through networking activities of all partners and projects of the 1st round in their communities, mainly through online events.

The next phase (months 22 to 33) was affected by the communication about the 2nd round of the ACTION Accelerator and the participating pilots, the promotion of the six [ACTION policy masterclasses](#), the participation of ACTION in a Horizon dissemination booster cluster as well as the preparation of the ACTION final conference.

The final phase (months 34 to 36) included the successful implementation of the ACTION final conference "[The future of citizen science](#)" with more than 160 participants, 30 speakers and 20 virtual

¹ Reeves, N. (2020). [Summary of Round One \(ACTION D3.3\)](#)

booths, the final European masterclass with the resulting [policy recommendations](#), as well as the planning of the legacy of the project dissemination channels.

Throughout all phases networking and exchange with related EU projects (e.g. [EU-Citizen.Science](#), [REINFORCE](#), [MICS](#), [TERRIFICA](#), [WeCount](#) and others) as well as scientific dissemination was an important project activity with the publication of first peer-reviewed articles, and presentations and posters at conferences (cf. chapter 3.9).

In the next chapter details on the single activities and related statistics are presented, followed by the summarising table of key performance indicators and achieved figures.

3 ACTION DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION AND NETWORKING ACHIEVEMENTS

3.1 ACTION identity, brand and design of project outputs

The ACTION identity (cf. Figure 1) was realised in a co-design process with the entire ACTION consortium at the beginning of the project and has been used throughout all dissemination materials and channels and became a well-established symbol of the project.

Figure 1: ACTION banner on social media.

At the event of the project two outputs were professionally designed: the [policy recommendations](#) to mainstream citizen science in policy (output of the Policy masterclasses) as well as the ACTION Toolkit.

3.2 ACTION website

The ACTION website (actionproject.eu) was the main online dissemination tool, together with the social media channels. It will be the legacy tool of the project, at least staying online for further four years after the end of the project. The website is hosted by the ACTION partner Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM). Until the end of the project, the ACTION website has presented the project and its on-going activities as well as key results and outputs.

It underwent several major revisions, following the development of the project. While the development and structure of the first 15 months have been presented in D7.1 and 7.2, in the following we describe the updated structure, as the website was considerably changed at the beginning of the second half of the project (also integrating comments from the interim review):

The *Homepage* (cf. Figure 2) provided users with an overview on the main project activities at a glance:

Figure 2: ACTION Homepage (mid of January 2022).

- A slide show at the top showed the most important news, activities and results as well as the core values of the project (openness, diversity, innovation and sustainability);
- A short description of the project and the video of the European Commission “Citizen Science: Opening up science to society”, in which ACTION is featured;
- A second slide show introduced the visitors to the ACTION Citizen Science projects: a short description of the projects accompanied with photos gives visitors an immediate visual overview on them;
- “Whom is ACTION for?” Here it was described for each target group what ACTION could provide to them in terms of new training, tools, etc.;
- Four parallel boxes showed the main project outputs (Toolkit, Accelerator, Masterclasses, Open Calls), giving the reader an immediate information on the services and outputs ACTION develops;
- “Latest news” provided news from the ACTION activities, e.g. the research or the pilots;
- The section “Contact form and newsletter subscription” ended the Home page offering the opportunity to the visitors to keep in touch with the project team.

The majority of the above-mentioned sub-sections of the Home Page were linked with other pages of the website where visitors can access further information.

The project website contained the following additional pages:

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- [About](#) was the main part of the website where the project and the project consortium was described.
- [Citizen Science Pilots](#):
 - an overview page of all ACTION pilots, divided by the CS projects involved since the beginning of the project, the ones selected through the 1st Open call and those selected by the 2nd Open Call. From this page single project pages of all projects could be opened;
 - Single project pages, following a common structure. Each project had an overview box, showing the location, the type of pollution as well as Sustainable Development Goals addressed, number of citizen scientists involved and information about if the pilot is looking for additional participants. This was followed by a longer project description, how interested readers can participate, what is novel and innovative, pilots' media and latest news.
- [News](#) (cf. Figure 3) was the repository of project and Citizen Science pilots' news as well as news on citizen science in general. The category of each news item was easily visible. The most recent news could be found on the Homepage. ACTION partners and projects were actively contributing to this section of the website: a rotation system was in place to ensure new and diversified content on a regular basis. The dissemination team developed guidelines supporting partners in creating news and stories for the website and assuring that all dissemination events carried out by them are opportunely reported on the website (and on social media).

Figure 3: ACTION News page (mid of January 2022).

- The [Accelerator](#) page, in addition to describing the support programme step by step, contained subpages for the Open Calls, the Dashboard (pilots' factsheet) as well as to the webinars implemented within the Accelerator.
- [Masterclasses](#): this page (cf. Figure 4) provided information on the six ACTION masterclasses with a link to the registration page for the individual masterclasses. Therefore the page was continuously updated.

Figure 4: ACTION Masterclasses page (mid of January 2022).

- **Toolkit:** this page was created and will remain as an interactive space in which users were able to access the different instruments, following the participatory science lifecycle. In an intermediary version (later summer and autumn 2021) a feedback button was added where users had the opportunity to comment and suggest changes. In the near future the page will also give the possibility for downloading a pdf of the toolkit (at the time of writing of this report the work was still undergoing).
- The **Resources** page made most ACTION outputs available, divided by categories. It also linked to the ACTION Open Science Portal which, in addition to the website page offered access to datasets, etc..
- **Contacts** included a form to be used for writing to the project team, make available the “info” mail address of the project and hosted the subscribe button through which visitors can subscribe to the joint newsletter of CS projects supported by the SwafS (Science with and for Society) programme and coordinated by the EU-citizen.science project (cf. chapter 3.4).

The ACTION website had attracted more than 26,000 visitors (who spent on average 1.47 minutes on the site) and more than 82,000 pages views, with a base of nearly 15% returning visitors and 85% of new visitors. As in regard to the visitors in the first 15 months (about 8,000), this is a considerable increase which can be understood as a result of the community building with the pilots and the networking with other citizen science initiatives. The website had several peaks in the

number of visits: one in September 2019 and another in October 2019, thanks to the Open Call promotion campaign. Two more peaks occurred in relation to the 2nd Open Call promotion campaign in September and October 2020. The highest peak was around the 2nd Accelerator kick-off meeting and the first weeks of the training in January/February 2021 with more than 1.100 visitors per day. The main channels of incoming traffic were approximately: direct (40% - people who directly enter the URL of ACTION website), organic search (nearly 38% - people who find the website through Google researches or other search engines), referral (nearly 14% - people who click on the link of the website), social (8% - people who click on the link via Facebook, Twitter or YouTube). The rest is “other” and “email”.

Legacy version: At the end of the project the website has been redesigned in order to be the main archive of all ACTION outputs and of the project activities. The website will stay online for at least four more years. In order to remain compelling for the different ACTION target groups, the homepage shows the main outputs and names the main target groups. The Toolkit and Resources pages have a prominent role, as all reports and other outputs can be found there. Other content stays, but it is adapted to the fact that the project has finished, e.g. the description of the project itself and the various activities (including the events and the newsletter, etc.). The news are shown in an archive and the links to the social media channels and e.g. the newsletter are deleted.

3.3 ACTION social media

ACTION was using two social media channels: Twitter and Facebook. Twitter was used mainly for getting in touch with established CS actors, researchers in the field and other EU projects; while Facebook was used for reaching out to the general public and to grassroots initiatives interested in CS. Facebook was also a channel for well-established CS initiatives, but less so than Twitter. We also had a YouTube channel, but we used it mainly as an online repository for our video contents that have been then promoted via the project website, Twitter and Facebook. As described in D7.1 we bootstrapped ACTION social media channels with the partners help, which has been crucial also in terms of content generation and followers’ growth. Indeed, considering all the followers of all ACTION partners we could count almost 350,000 followers on Twitter and more than 645,000 on Facebook. The support of the partners in the dissemination activities was therefore crucial and proved to be effective throughout the project.

3.3.1 ACTION Twitter account

The [ACTION Twitter profile](#) was opened in April 2019. Our profile was steadily growing during the duration of the project, especially on tweet impressions, thanks to Retweets (RTs) and mentions from other accounts, especially the ones from the ACTION partners. As of January 2022, the ACTION project Twitter account gained 858 followers and an average of more than 16,300 tweet views per month. Our main strengths were contributions from the partners that we tweeted, e.g. information on their actual project activities, research of the pilots, events and similar. This was supported by shares of ACTION contents on personal accounts and joining the conversation.

There were **six peaks** of more than 40,000 views in conjunction with two important events:

1. The first in October 2019, at the end of the 1st Open Call and the second in February 2020 in relation to the ACTION Accelerator kick-off meeting in Berlin (cf. D7.2);
2. The third peak was in September 2020, at the launch of the 2nd Open Call (cf. Figure 5);
3. The fourth peak was in October 2020, for the end of the 2nd Open Call and thanks to some partners' content (cf. Figure 6) that helped us reach almost 35,000 views. One in particular reached more than 7,000 views by itself, because the project was very interesting for our audience;
4. The fifth peak was in January 2021, thanks to the featuring of ACTION in the European Commission video. The tweet announcing the feature reached more than 8,000 views by itself. The month of January 2021 reached more than 43,000 views thanks also to the launch of the second Accelerator programme;
5. The sixth peak was in November 2021, in relation to the final conference and related tweets.

Figure 5: Post during the launch of the second open call and related statistics.

Figure 6: Post about Street Spectra project and related statistics.

Top Tweets:

Figure 7 shows two typical posts from a partner. The news were short but straightforward. A lot of mentions and a good photo made the tweet remarkable and effective. The left post was seen almost 3,000 times, while the right one reached over 8,000 views.

Figure 7: Two examples with ACTION banners on social media.

Thanks to a lot of shares, we got 6,500 impressions on the Open Call tweet shown in Figure 8. The proactive tone of voice was part of the success of the Open Call tweet shown in Figure 9. It received almost 5,000 impressions, also because the Open Call produced a lot of interest in the Citizen Science community.

Figure 8: Top Tweet ACTION banner on social media on the 2nd Open Call.

Figure 9: Top Tweet ACTION banner on social media on the 1st Open Call.

In relation to the first 15 months, in the second part of the project, from May 2020 to January 2022, we worked more on what the CS community really appreciated: experiences from citizen science projects, results of our project and of course the 2nd Open Call. Our growth was steady but slow, more in terms of views and impressions than of followers. The reason for this follows a general trend: since March 2020 with the start of the Covid 19 pandemic there is a change of Twitter (and in general

social) audiences: people seemed to be more interested in other topics, like the pandemic. This means that people were generally more on the social networks, but searching and interacting with pandemics-related content and more polarising content in general.²

3.3.2 ACTION Facebook page

At the same time as the Twitter account, the [ACTION Facebook page](#) was created in April 2019. At the end of January 2022, it had 655 followers with a total reach of 120,000 people. The reach was around 40-70 people per post (every time we post, our content was seen by 40-70 people). This parameter did not depend on us because the Facebook algorithm decided what to show and to whom. The interaction included comments, clicks on the posts and shares. Our fanbase had a peak thanks to small advertising campaigns during the two Open Calls³ periods.

We experienced some larger peaks in some content thanks to relevant moments of dissemination, like the launch of Accelerator Programme or the Open Calls.

Facebook turned out to be a useful tool, especially during the Open Call phase: we mapped as many European CS pages and groups on Facebook as possible and advertised the call directly on their pages/communities. This demonstrated an additional way of enlarging the ACTION community and keeping it updated on project achievements also after the Open Calls.

During the Accelerator Kick-Off meetings in February 2020 and January 2021, the ACTION social media profiles were particularly active, as already shown in the previous chapter for Twitter. Thanks to this original and useful content, and to the sharing from partners and stakeholders, our social media profiles experienced a peak in performances and engagement.

Our most successful posts on Facebook were the ones on the Open Call. Indeed, the video-related post in Figure 10 reached more than 700 viewers and the post in Figure 11 reached more than one 1,100 people.

² Journalistic article on this topic: [How the coronavirus pandemic is changing social media](#) published on Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism website.

³ We ran two different Facebook Advertising Campaigns during the 1st Open Call (Sept-Oct 19). The first one had the goal to gain more followers to the fan page. We reached 13,400 impressions and 5,800 people with 403 likes gained. The other campaign had the goal to reach more people with the Open Call post. The campaign was active from 13 to 19 Sept 19 and it reached more than 10,000 people with 522 interactions.

During the 2nd Open Call (Sept-Oct 20) we ran a Facebook Advertising Campaign. We reached 106,526 people and 260,295 impressions and almost 23,000 interactions.

Figure 10: Example of posts to promote the 2nd Open Call.

Figure 11: Example of the adv post to promote the 2nd Open Call.

Other posts that were significant in terms of engagement and outreach were the ones in relation to major announcements and good visuals. Figure 12 shows a post that announced four new pilots of the 2nd round of the Accelerator in March 2021, with almost 1,000 people reached, 64 reactions and 7 shares. Figure 13 shows a post on the promotion of a webinar with more than 920 persons reached.

Figure 12: Announcement of 4 new ACTION pilots (March 2021).

Figure 13: The promotion of a webinar (November 2020).

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The Facebook page also experienced some peaks in terms of organic reach and engagement. One was during the ACTION final conference (cf. Figure 14), another was the Citizen Science Italia event (cf. Figure 15) (both in November 2021), when we promoted the Italian masterclass reaching almost 700 people with almost 50 interactions.

Figure 14: Promotion of ACTION Final conference.

Figure 15: Promotion of Italian masterclass.

As the Italian masterclass was a side event of the Citizen Science Italia national meeting, this was a good occasion to reach the citizen science community in Italy (Figures 16 and 17).

Figure 16: Post Citizen Science conference Italia by ACTION (November 2021).

Figure 17: Post on Italian masterclass (November 2021).

To conclude, the social media activities of ACTION can be considered active and successful, considering the fast development of the social media landscape and business models of Twitter and Facebook as well as the change in user behaviour and taking into account that we followed also a decentralized strategy counting on the support of the project partners.

At the end of the project both channels will be closed, with a concluding message and pointing to other channels on future related activities (e.g. those of the eu-citizen.science project).

3.4 Newsletter

As described in D7.1, as a result of the collaboration with the [EU-citizen.science project](#), it was decided that the coordination and support action for the SwafS programme dedicated to CS should develop a joint newsletter for all projects funded under the same H2020 call (ACTION, Cities Health, D-NOSES, EU-Citizen.Science and MICS). The joint newsletter on citizen science was an occasion to liaise with the other projects in the field and strengthen the ties of a European community of citizen science. By the end of the ACTION project six joint newsletters had been published and ACTION news or contributions covered the Open Calls, the ACTION pilots, the Accelerator activities and the toolkit.

By the time of writing this report, 800 people have subscribed to the newsletter and the number of subscribers has been steadily growing from one edition to the other as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Subscribers and open rate of joint newsletter

Newsletter editions	Date	Number of subscribers	Open rate (%)	Open rate (Number)
Presentation of the project and of the newsletter	Jun-19	87	73,6	64
Air pollution	Oct-19	298	45,6	136
Inclusion	Feb-20	401	52,6	211
COVID-19 pandemic	Jul-20	565	38,7	217
Citizen science and the SDGs	Nov-20	647	48,8	313
End of the EU-Citizen.Science project: Upcoming activities and outcomes from all the citizen science projects	Jan-22	800	41,3	323

3.5 Videos and webinar recordings

ACTION realised 13 videos and several video clips. In addition to the three videos in the first 15 months, additional 10 were produced in the other 21 months.

Topics covered by the videos were (all available [here](#)):

- Presentation of ACTION and the Street Spectra pilot (developed by the UPM team) - integrated on the About page of the ACTION website;
- Presentation of the 1st and 2nd Open Call (two different videos);

- Step by step explanation on how to participate in the 1st and 2nd Open Call (two different videos);
- “The future of citizen science” (ACTION final conference) presentations and discussions: four full registrations of the various sessions (including masterclass) and four short summaries of the sessions that can be used for dissemination on social media.

In addition, short video interviews, one with each of the ACTION partners, were filmed during the project meeting in Rome in June 2019, introducing the partner organisations and their role in the project. ACTION partners leading one or more citizen science pilot projects have been further interviewed in order to realise a short video presentation of each pilot and some ACTION pilots have made short videos about their projects. These presentations were shared on the ACTION social media channels.

The videos in regard to the final conference are available on the [ECSCA - European Citizen Science Association YouTube channel](#). All other videos are available on the [ACTION YouTube channel](#).

Furthermore, most of the Accelerator training webinars, the webinar about financial sustainability as well as two webinars organised by ACTION pilots were registered and are available on the [ACTION YouTube channel](#) and the [Resources page](#) of the ACTION website.

Considering all ACTION videos and webinar registrations, they were viewed nearly 2,400 times through YouTube and many more times on social media.

3.6 Partners' websites, blogs and other dissemination channels

ACTION partners were fully engaged in the communication and dissemination activities, not only by creating news and posts for the ACTION website and social media accounts, but also through their own - personal and institutional - communication channels as mentioned in the previous paragraphs for reposting and retweeting ACTION news and posts and disseminate ACTION news in their networks.

3.7 ACTION dissemination material

As reported in D7.2 a project factsheet was developed at the beginning of the project. For the second half of the project, we intended to develop a brochure, providing more information about ACTION but, especially, about its pilot projects. However, due to the fact that project dissemination took merely place online (including the project final conference), and that the information about the projects was continuously changing during their implementation, it was decided to not realise a brochure, but to make the individual projects' pages on the ACTION website more informative and to put more attention on the regular update of the project website as well as the standard presentation of the project. In addition to this, the toolkit as well as the policy recommendations were designed in a way that they provide information about ACTION and remain as important outputs of the project even after it ends.

3.8 Scientific publications

Up to today, 24 peer-reviewed papers have been published, all with Open Access (cf. Table 2).

Table 2: Peer-reviewed publications realised by the ACTION partners

Title	Authors	Title of the Journal/Proc./Book	Number, date or freq. of the Journal/Proc./Book	DOI
Magnitude to luminance conversions and visual brightness of the night sky	Salvador Bará, Martin Aubé, John Barentine, Jaime Zamorano	Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society	493/2	10.1093/mnras/staa323
Environmental levels of neonicotinoids reduce prey consumption, mobility and emergence of the damselfly <i>Ischnura elegans</i>	S. Henrik Barmentlo, Laura M. Vriend, Roy H. A. Grunsven, Martina G. Vijver	Journal of Applied Ecology		10.1111/1365-2664.13459
Who Is This Explanation for? Human Intelligence and Knowledge Graphs for eXplainable AI	Irene Celino	Knowledge Graphs for eXplainable AI -- Foundations, Applications and Challenges. Studies on the Semantic Web	47	10.3233/ssw200024
Efficient, but Effective?	Neal T. Reeves, Elena Simperl	Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction	3/CSCW	10.1145/3359279
Submitting surveys via a conversational interface: An evaluation of user acceptance and approach effectiveness	Irene Celino, Gloria Re Calegari	International Journal of Human-Computer Studies	139	10.1016/j.ijhcs.2020.102410
Evaluating Human Photoreceptor Inputs from Night-Time Lights Using RGB Imaging Photometry	Alejandro Sánchez de Miguel, Salvador Bará, Martin Aubé, Nicolás Cardiel, Carlos E. Tapia, Jaime Zamorano, Kevin J. Gaston	Journal of Imaging	5/4	10.3390/ijmagi5040049
Multispectral estimation of retinal photoreceptor inputs	Salvador Bara, Maria Angeles Bonmati-Carrion, Juan Antonio Madrid, Maria Angeles Rol, Jaime Zamorano	Photonics Letters of Poland	11/3	10.4302/plp.v11i3.920
Standardized spectral and radiometric calibration of consumer cameras	Olivier Burggraaff, Norbert Schmidt, Jaime Zamorano, Klaas Pauly, Sergio Pascual, Carlos Tapia, Evangelos Spyarakos, Frans Snik	Optics Express	27/14	10.1364/oe.27019075
Monitoring Long-Term Trends in the Anthropogenic Night Sky Brightness	Salvador Bará, Raul C. Lima, Jaime Zamorano	Sustainability	11/11	10.3390/su1113070

Transformative Potential and Learning Outcomes of Air Quality Citizen Science Projects in High Schools Using Low-Cost Sensors	Sonja Grossberndt; Antonella Passani; Giulia Di Lisio; Anelli Janssen; Nuria Castell	Atmosphere	12(6)	10.3390/atmos12060736
Direct assessment of the sensitivity drift of SQM sensors installed outdoors	Bará, Salvador; Marco, Enric; Ribas, Salvador J.; Gil, Manuel Garcia; de Miguel, Alejandro Sánchez; Zamorano, Jaime	International Journal of Sustainable Lighting, Vol 23, Iss 1 (2021)		10.26607/ijsl.v23i1.109
Synthetic RGB photometry of bright stars: definition of the standard photometric system and UCM library of spectrophotometric spectra	Nicolás Cardiel; Jaime Zamorano; Salvador Bará; Alejandro Sánchez de Miguel; Cristina Cabello; Jesús Gallego; Lucía García; Rafael González; Jaime Izquierdo; Sergio Pascual; José Robles; Ainhoa Sánchez; Carlos Tapia	Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society	Volume 504, Issue 3, July 2021	10.1093/mnras/stab997
RGB photometric calibration of 15 million Gaia stars	Cardiel López, Nicolás; Zamorano Calvo, Jaime; Bará, Salvador; Sánchez de Miguel, Alejandro; Cabello González, Cristina; Gallego Maestro, Jesús; García, Lucía; González, Rafael; Izquierdo Gómez, Jaime; Pascual Ramírez, Sergio; Sánchez Penim, Ainhoa; Tapia Ayuga, Carlos	Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society	Volume 507, Issue 1, October 2021	10.1093/mnras/stab2124
CONEY: A CONversational survey Toolkit	Scandolari, Damiano; Calegari, Gloria Re; Scrocca, Mario; Celino, Irene	13th Biannual Conference of the Italian SIGCHI Chapter (CHIItaly 2019), Padua, Italy, September 23-25, 2019		10.5281/zenodo.3446014
We don't need no expectations: on the observer-expectancy effect in crowdsourcing	Eddy Maddalena, Alessandro Checco and Elena Simperl	Third symposium on Biases in Human Computation and Crowdsourcing (BCC2021)	2021	
Microplastic inclusion in birch tree roots	Kat Austen, Joana McLean, Daniel Balanzategui and Franz Hölker	Science of the Total Environment	808	10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.152085
Towards Insect-Friendly Road Lighting—A Transdisciplinary Multi-Stakeholder Approach Involving Citizen Scientists	Sibylle Schroer, Kat Austen, Nicola Moczek, Gregor Kalinkat, Andreas Jechow, Stefan Heller, Johanna Reinhard, Sophia Dehn, Charis I. Wuthenow, Martin Post-Stapelfeldt, Roy H. A. van Grunsven, Catherine Pérez Vega, Heike	Insects	12(12)	10.3390/insects12121117

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Evolution of Brightness and Color of the Night Sky in Madrid	José Robles, Jaime Zamorano, Sergio Pascual, Alejandro Sánchez de Miguel, Jesús Gallego and Kevin J. Gaston	Remote Sensing	13(8)	10.3390/rs13081511
An analysis of pollution Citizen Science projects from the perspective of Data Science and Open Science	Roman, Dumitru; Reeves, Neal; Gonzalez, Esteban; Celino, Irene; Abd El Kader, Shady; Turk, Philip; Soyulu, Ahmet; Óscar Corcho; Cedazo, Raquel; Re Calegari, Gloria; Scandolari, Damiano; Simperl, Elena	Data Technologies and Applications	55(5)	10.1108/dta-10-2020-0253
Coney: a conversational approach to enhance engagement in surveys	Damiano Scandolari; Mario Scrocca; Gloria Re Calegari; Irene Celino;	Open Science Fair 2019 (OSFair 2019), Porto, 16-18 September 2019 (Session Demos)		10.5281/zenodo.5846755
Participant motivation to engage in a citizen science campaign: the case of the TESS network	Irene Celino; Gloria Re Calegari; Mario Scrocca; Jaime Zamorano; Esteban Gonzalez Guardia	Journal of Science Communication	6	10.22323/2.20060203
Participant motivation to engage in a citizen science campaign: the case of the TESS network	Calegari, Gloria Re; Celino, Irene; Scrocca, Mario; González, Esteban; Zamorano, Jaime	ECSCA Conference 2020		10.5281/zenodo.4068332
The Survey Ontology: Packaging Survey Research as Research Objects	Mario Scrocca; Damiano Scandolari; Gloria Re Calegari; Ilaria Baroni; Irene Celino	2nd Workshop on Data and Research Objects Management for Linked Open Science (DaMaLOS),		10.4126/frl01-006429412

The publications cover a wide range of project results and were developed through a close collaboration of the ACTION partners.

3.9 Presentations and participation at events

The research and innovation outputs of the project and the achievements of the citizen science pilots were primarily disseminated through publications and talks at different types of events – conferences, workshops, and networking events with other SwafS projects, for different types of target audiences, e.g. citizen science projects and researchers, NGOs, policy makers and administration at various levels and to citizen scientists and at events for an interested public.

These are presented in the following, divided by presentations, posters and participation in events.

ACTION partners gave 31 presentations and talks at the following external roundtables, workshops and conferences (*note: some events do not have working links anymore; therefore they were not added*):

- Workshop on citizen science at [Foro internacional de Ciencia Ciudadana](#) (March 2019)
- Open Day Dutch Butterfly Conservation (March 2019);
- [Annual meeting of Dutch Dragonfly Association](#) (NVL) (March 2019);
- Light Pollution: Theory, Modelling and Measurements at LPTMM2019 (June 2019);
- [Open Science Fair](#), Porto (including a demo) (September 2019);
- Casa das Ciencias - Planetario A Coruña (II Encontro da Noite) (October 2019);
- Let's do it Together. Event at UPM on Open Science supported by the FIT4RRI project (November 2019);
- [Koppeling](#) (January 2020);
- [Synergy Conference](#) (workshop) (February 2020);
- "Westminster Higher Education Forum policy conference. Open research data in the UK - next steps for implementing the Plan S proposals", London (February 2020);
- Resistance is in the Air: Citizens, science and air pollution; [International interdisciplinary symposium](#), Brussels (April 2019);
- Presentation to Norwegian teachers about air quality (October 2019);
- "Mapping the "How" of Collaborative Action: Research Methods for Studying Contemporary Sociotechnical Processes" at CSCW 2020, Austin, Texas (November 2019);
- Support in preparation of the workshop "Science for Citizens: how science meets regions and cities" (with more than 100 participants) during the European Week of Cities and Regions 2019 where ACTION was presented by the EU-Citizen.Science project (October 2019);
- [ACM-W UK Webinar Series: Computing for Social Good](#) (June 2020);
- [Citizen Science Conference 2020: Knowledge for Change: A decade of Citizen Science \(2020-030\) in support of the SDGs](#) (October 2020);
- [Data Stories Symposium](#) (November 2020);
- [ENDORSE 1st European Data Conference on Reference Data and Semantics](#) (March 2021);
- Talk for UK CO Policy Lab (May 2021);
- Moderation of discussion "[New European Bauhaus and our Backyards](#)" (May 2021);
- [8th STS Italia Conference](#) (June 2021);
- [9th ACM Conference on Collective Intelligence 2021](#) (June 2021);
- [Citizen Science Clinic: Impact assessment frameworks](#) (June 2021);
- [Living Knowledge Conference](#) (June 2021);
- [1st Global Transdisciplinarity Conference](#) (September 2021);
- Colloquium for master students at Aarhus university (October 2021);
- [2nd Workshop on Data and research objects management for Linked Open Science co-located with ISWC](#) (October 2021);
- [Citizen Science Italia - annual meeting](#) (November 2021);
- [Blumen! The Science Show](#) at Berlin Science Week (December 2021).

Overall, these talks reached approximately 2,800 people, mainly academics, policy makers and administration, citizen science projects and practitioners, related EU projects as well as the general public.

12 posters were presented at the following conferences:

- 5 posters at [LPTMM2019](#) (June 2019);
- Engaging Billions of Scientists! Citizen Science Workshop. The Hague, Netherlands (July 2019);
- CHIItaly, Padova (September 2019);
- III Congreso pro-Am from Sociedad Española de Astronomía (December 2019);
- III SEA-Proam workshop, Spain (December 2019);
- [e-ALAN2020](#) (June 2020);
- Two posters at [ECSA Conference 2020](#) (September 2020).

The posters reached more than 1,200 people.

Additionally, ACTION researchers participated in the following six events:

- Workshop “Data governance from principles to practice: Civil society, volunteer data science skills, and open datasets”, London (March 2020);
- 'Citizens' information pack' workshop, Berlin (March 2020);
- DITOS Final Closing Event (April 2019);
- Co-design workshop organised by EU.CitizenScience (April 2019);
- Horizon 2020 citizen science cluster meeting by EC (December 2019);
- [Digitranscope Spring Institute](#) (October 2020).

On all occasions with a total number of approx. 300 participants ACTION was promoted.

3.10 ACTION events

The consortium has organised a large number of events with training and interactive sessions as part of the ACTION Accelerator, policy masterclasses as well as workshops at citizen science project level. In addition, several events were organised in collaboration with related projects, e.g. workshops at policy events. Among these collaboratively organised events was the ACTION final conference “The future of citizen science” which is described in the next chapter. Some of the policy masterclasses and the Accelerator kick-off meeting were done in presence, while all other events were held online. ACTION partners did talks in most of these events.

Events in regard to support for the Open Calls:

- Three support webinars for 1st Open Call (August, September and October 2019);
- Two support webinars for 2nd Open Call (September and October 2020).

Events in relation to the ACTION Accelerator the following meetings and webinars took place:

- Accelerator kick-off meeting for the 1st round of projects (in person) (February 2020)⁴;
- Accelerator kick-off meeting for the 2nd round of projects (online) with presentations of all ACTION partners and from the ACTION pilots Noise Maps and In My Backyard;

⁴ Details on the 1st Accelerator kick-off meeting can be found in: Austen, K. (2020), [ACTION Workshop Report 1 \(D2.14\)](#); details on the 2nd Accelerator kick-off meeting in: Austen K. (2022), [ACTION Workshop Report 2: Practical Steps to Supporting Best Practice in Citizen Science \(D2.15\)](#).

- Accelerator webinars (Data Portal, Introduction to the Data Lifecycle; Grafana, Zenodo, GDPR, Data Collection, Data Processing (two parts); Data Management; Inclusion in Citizen Science; Diversity in Citizen Science (four meetings); Motivation in Citizen Science; Impact Assessment, Engaging Communities, Financial sustainability) (throughout 2020 and 2021);

ACTION partners organised the following dissemination events together with some of the pilots:

- Student conference in Oslo (April 2019);
- Villaverde del ducado (Guadalajara, Spain). Public astronomical observation (August 2019);
- Street Spectra tutorial at Asociación Astronómica de Madrid (October 2019);
- Workshop at Association of Amateur Astronomers from the Facultad de Ciencias Físicas of the Universidad Complutense de Madrid (ASAAF) (November 2019);
- Talk and hands on at Agrupación Astronómica de Madrid Sur (November 2019);
- Zero plastic event on Facebook by the CitiComPlastic pilot (February 2020);
- Online co-creation workshop with citizens by the CitiComPlastic pilot (April 2020);
- [Radio survey](#) about light pollution and the perception of artificial light at night in sleeping rooms (Radio 1 RBB, Germany) (September 2020);
- Kick-off Meeting for the launch of the Aube Project (October 2020);
- StreetSpectra trainings (October 2020 and 21 trainings in October and November 2021);
- Citizen Science Festival Mitforschen! (October 2020);
- Student workshops in Berlin (September 2020);
- Book a scientist (November 2021);
- Sociocracy webinar, co-organised with ACTION pilot Open Soil Atlas (November 2021);
- Preparation of the [first conference for citizen science in Norway](#) (November 2021);
- [ACTION Lab](#) at Ars Electronica 2020. The Festival for Art, Technology and Society “Ars Electronica” is an international platform for digital art and media culture that enjoys a worldwide reputation. During the ACTION Lab 6 ACTION pilots were presented (with respective videos and interactive sessions).

In order to reach a high number of policy makers, ACTION organised six policy masterclasses and, together with related projects, workshops and a coffee with partners-online session for the European Week of Regions and Cities in 2020 and 2021:

- Masterclasses in the Netherlands (April 2021), Norway (May 2021), the United Kingdom (June 2021), Spain (September 2021), Italy (November 2021) and one overarching in November 2021) with a total of 186 participants.
- Citizens Voices – Citizens Knowledge, [Workshop at 18th European Week of Regions and Cities 2020](#) in September 2020. This workshop was organised together with the Terrifica project. More than 60 participants listened to the presentations of introductions and of pilots from both projects, followed by a discussion on the growing interest in participatory activities for addressing environmental topics.
- [Coffee with partners](#) session at the European Week of Regions and Cities 2020, in collaboration with Terrifica (September 2020).
- Citizen science - tools to achieve a real impact on policy-making, [Workshop at 19th European Week of Regions and Cities](#). The workshop was jointly organised by the five European projects [ClairCity](#), [WeCount](#), [iSCAPE](#), [ICARUS](#) and [ACTION](#), all working on the involvement of citizens

in fighting the effects of environmental pollution and climate change. More than 60 participants joined the session. Key outcomes and lessons learned from the projects on improving air quality and urban mobility in European cities and reducing their carbon footprint by enhancing citizen engagement were presented, followed by a discussion. The collaboration was one result of the Horizon Results Booster in which these projects participated as a group (cf. chapter 4 below).

These events reached approx. 1,500 people.

3.11 The ACTION final conference "The future of citizen science"

The ACTION final conference "The future of citizen science" took place on 24th and 25th November 2021. It was organised together with the [EU-Citizen.Science](#) project.

The conference was structured in a way to provide citizen science community, citizen science projects, policy makers and administrations as well as academics with an opportunity for reciprocal learning and for meeting new persons. On 25th November in the afternoon the overarching ACTION policy masterclass was implemented as a satellite event to the conference.

The conference gathered more than 160 people, more than 30 [speakers](#) (of which 7 from the ACTION project) and more than 20 [virtual booths](#) in which citizen science projects (of which five ACTION pilots or projects) showcased their work.

The event was entirely online, using the Hopin platform. The overall organisation and facilitation was entrusted to [stickydot](#). Stickydot is a Brussels collective with expertise on multi-stakeholder engagement in research and innovation and supported the ACTION and [EU-Citizen.Science](#) project to define the structure and agenda of the conference and to facilitate the three main sessions.

The conference had three plenary sessions, three parallel workshops, coffee breaks in a social room and a fishbowl session. More information about the schedule, the speakers and the booths can be found [here](#).

All sessions, including the masterclass, were registered and were published as four videos (one for each half day) on the ACTION website [Resources page](#). They are also available on the [ECSA - European Citizen Science Association YouTube channel](#) and in this way ensure wider reach. Short summarising videos for each session were also produced and served for the promotion of the long registrations via social media.

Evaluation

At the end of the event, participants were asked to fill in an evaluation questionnaire anonymously. They were asked to rate the overall quality, the technical set-up, networking opportunities, the expo area and the communication before and during the event. Responders could also add main takeaways, main strengths and areas of improvements as well as other comments. 37 responses arrived, mainly from researchers (91%). 70% of respondents participated in the whole conference and 40% also at the satellite policy event.

Overall, the evaluation was very positive.

In particular the overall quality of the sessions as well as the technical set up was rated as excellent, good and fair by nearly all respondents. The networking opportunities were evaluated by more than

27 respondents as excellent, good and fair, the remaining ones gave no answer. The exhibition got an equal number of excellent (8), good (9) and fair (8), 2 rated it as poor, the rest gave no answer. 83% were familiar with either the ACTION or the EU-Citizen.Science project or with projects before the event: this meant that the event also reached persons outside our already large network.

Among the *strengths of the conference* it was mentioned that it gave a good overview on the citizen science landscape in Europe, covering both the academic as well as the policy approach. The structure and moderation of the conference and the high quality of speakers were other strengths mentioned several times.

Among the *main takeaways* it was mentioned that:

- the events showed a concrete perspective that citizen science could be mainstreamed at the EU level and that it has a growing importance;
- the citizen science landscape is very diverse (which is a strength) but therefore needs strong networking; however, also room for disciplinary spaces is needed;
- citizen science is gaining attention from many governments so that there is room for strategies and actions;
- good ideas for the assessment of citizen science projects;
- approximately 1/3 of an investment for a citizen science project needs to be dedicated to lift citizen participation

Suggestions for improvements were in relation to contents:

- to involve more policy-makers;
- to focus more on practical issues of citizen science, as e.g. establishing and running projects, overview of current policy experiences in different countries as well as practical lessons learned from projects.

As further room for improvements was mentioned, apart from some technical problems, increased possibility for networking, a better promotion of the exhibition and to have the possibility to get the agenda before the event as a pdf file.

Summarising the evaluation, the event was overall very successful and interactive, although being completely online (which might have allowed a wider audience to participate). For future events more practical aspects of citizen science projects might attract more practitioners and the involvement of more policy-makers from different levels should be ensured.

3.12 Articles, press releases and outreach to the media

Different aspects of the project were disseminated mainly through interviews and one article. In addition, press releases were published in connection with all relevant events and outcomes.

Interviews and articles:

- 2 radio interviews at [Radio Internacional](#) (June 2019) and [Radio Voz](#) (January 2020), both in Spain, on dragonflies and street spectra projects;
- Interview “[The power of the crowd: How citizen science can help preserve the environment](#)” in September 2021 for [Wärtsilä.com](#);

- Article "[Exploring the impact of a Citizen Science high school project](#)" in the CS track magazine (September 2021);
- Interview with CitiMeasure project by NILU (although ACTION is not mentioned explicitly, the activities are) (January 2022);
- Citizen science manifesto "Empowering citizens to engage in co-creating healthier, more environment and climate friendly metropolitan areas" of Horizon Results Booster "Residents Striving for Sustainable Cities", published on all participating projects' websites.

Seven press releases were published:

- Presentation of ACTION project (February 2019);
- Open Call for citizen science projects (September 2020);
- First four ACTION pilots successfully graduated: congratulations! (October 2020);
- New pilots starting! (March 2021);
- ACTION Accelerator kick-off meeting (January 2021);
- Policy recommendations published - communication campaign (January 2022);
- ACTION toolkit published - communication campaign (planned for February 2022).

The press releases were sent to all project partners for further dissemination to their media contacts. ACTION published various press announcements of the pilot projects, e.g. in regard to upcoming events.

4 COLLABORATION AND NETWORKING WITH CITIZEN SCIENCE COMMUNITY AND PARTNERSHIPS WITH OTHER EU PROJECTS

The ACTION consortium started to build a community around the project from the very beginning, starting from the extensive network of each of the partners in citizen science research and related disciplines. During the ACTION kick-off meeting the initial mapping of stakeholders has been updated and representatives of this initial ecosystem have been invited to become reviewers of the 1st and 2nd Open Call.

The strategy followed by the ACTION dissemination team was that of preparing materials to be disseminated to the ecosystem without centralizing this activity. In other terms, ACTION partners disseminated key messages coming from the project to their networks in key moments of the project, such as the Open Calls, activities and results of the pilots and the Accelerator as well as the promotion of dissemination activities and events. In this way the project did not create a centralised database of contacts (which will show some challenges considering the GDPR regulation) and recipients received information from a trusted contact and not from yet another EU project. The results of this strategy were visible in the number of followers we had on key tweets and news on our social media and on our website (cf. chapters 3.2 and 3.3) as well as the number of participants in events such as the final conference or the workshops at the European Week of Regions and Cities. The network around ACTION will be an asset for the sustainability of the community after the end of the project funding period (cf. D7.5) because in this way ACTION actually helps each project partner to become more visible on the CS topic and enlarges its already-existing network.

Central has been the collaboration with other EU projects working on CS: thanks to the action of [EU-Citizen-science](#), a Coordination Action project, ACTION got in contact with all the projects working on CS financed by the SwafS programme and actively contributed to structure the agendas for regular calls and regularly presenting project updates. As mentioned in Chapter 3.4, ACTION also decided to accede to the joint newsletter, coordinated by EU-citizen.science. Another strong collaboration took place for the planning and implementation of the conference “The future of citizen science” which was organised by both projects in an equal way. Beside this, thanks to the regular meeting with other SwafS projects, strong links have been established with CTrack, COESO and [REINFORCE](#), with whom we are collaborating at dissemination level sharing information and providing reciprocal visibility to key news through our website and social media channels.

A strong opportunity for networking was also the Horizon 2020 citizen science cluster meeting, organised by the European Commission in December 2019.

A more intense exchange happened with the [MICS](#) project which is developing an impact assessment framework for CS in order to share knowledge and opportunities on this topic which is relevant also for ACTION. Thanks to the suggestions coming from the SwafS unit of the European Commission, a collaboration with the [TERRIFICA](#) project happened for the organisation of a workshop at the European Week of Cities and Regions 2020 event. On the same line, ACTION, TERRIFICA and [Crowd4SDG](#) participated together at the EU R&I days in 2020.

In 2021 ACTION enlarged its networking activities outside the SwafS domain and joined the Horizon Results Booster “Residents Striving for Sustainable Cities”. This group started as a collaboration between the three projects [ClairCity](#), [ICARUS](#) and [iSCAPE](#), funded under the Horizon 2020 call “Improving the air quality and reducing the carbon footprint of European cities”. All three projects had a strong citizen science and engagement part. In order to strengthen the group, the SwafS projects [WeCount](#) and [ACTION](#) joined. The Booster (supporting the projects in promoting common results) led to the common organisation of the workshop [Citizen science - tools to achieve a real impact on policy-making](#), at the 19th European Week of Regions and Cities in October 2021. In addition the group developed a manifesto Empowering citizens to engage in co-creating healthier, more environment and climate friendly metropolitan areas which will be disseminated through all projects’ websites. The booster finished in December 2021.

5 DISSEMINATION IMPACT ASSESSMENT

The implementation of the communication and dissemination strategy was monitored through the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that had been identified in the DoA and D7.1. In the following Table 3, the achieved numbers are shown for the two reporting periods: February 2019 - April 2020 and May 2020 - January 2022) as well as for the whole duration of the project and a short analysis for each KPI is added, summarising and completing the numbers presented in the previous chapters. The numbers are based on information from all ACTION consortium members as well as tracking ACTION dissemination activities. A final interpretation can be found in chapter 6.

Table 3: ACTION communication and dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and results for the periods February 2019 - April 2020 and May 2020 - January 2022, as well as for the whole duration of the project (36 months)

Instrument	Indicator	Target for the whole project duration (36 months)	Achieved results M1-15 months	Achieved results M16-36	Achieved results after 36 months	Analysis and means of verification
Flyer/postcards	Number of designs Flyer/postcard distributed online and offline	2 >1k by the end of M18 >2k by the end of M36	1 App. 250 open call postcard distributed in paper format. The online version was used also on social media (cf. twitter statistics).	1 The postcard was mainly realised for online dissemination. It was not printed as the promotion took mainly place online.	2	The distribution of the call took place mainly online, via the website and on social media, etc. Therefore the distribution of postcards was limited. However, it can be assumed that this did not reduce the number of applications.
Posters/roll-up	Number of designs, updated if needed	2	2	0	2	The poster templates have been used in 12 events. Roll-ups were not produced, as most events took place online.
Publications	Number of journal and conference papers	10+	9	15	24	The consortium published peer-reviewed scientific

						journals and books. See ACTION project community on Zenodo.
Talks	Number of talks	50 for the entire duration of the project	13	46	59	Presentations and invited talks at events, including workshops, conferences, webinars, Accelerator kick-off meetings, etc (cf. chapters 3.9-3.11).
Videos	Number of videos Views per video	2 videos with 500+ online views per video	3 videos and several video interviews	10	13 with 2,400 views of all videos throughout our YouTube channels	List of all videos is shown in chapter 3.5.
Project website	Number of visits + page visits	1.5k visitors, 3k pages views	8k visitors, with almost 24k page views	18,7 k visitors, with almost 58k page views	26,7k visitors with more than 82k pages views	Web traffic statistics collected and documented in this deliverable.
	Average duration of visits	One minute	1:43 minutes			
Social media	Number of followers on Twitter and Facebook	3k by the end of the project	954 summing Facebook and Twitter	559 summing Facebook and Twitter	1,513 summing	Social media analytics collected and documented in this deliverable. The project was

						very active on social media. It is assumed that the changed social media user behaviour (cf. chapter 3.3) was the reason for not reaching the planned target followers. In addition we used a decentralised strategy, involving the partners channels.
Co-design and policy workshops	Number of events Average number of attendees	15-20 rapid prototyping workshops (150 participants) 1 methodological co-design workshop (20-25 participants) 1 data analysis workshop (20-25 participants) 6 policy masterclasses (15-20 participants each)	Some of the prototyping workshops have been done during the Accelerator kick-off meeting, others online bilaterally with the new pilots due to the Covid-19 lockdown with the mentors. More will be done when the additional pilots of the 2 nd Open Call	The prototyping and data analysis workshops were reorganised and done bilaterally with the pilots. The six masterclasses were implemented with more participants as planned (in total 186).	See single description for each period.	All planned co-design activities have been implemented, although partly in different forms than planned. It was preferred to do co-design activities mainly bilaterally with the pilots, due to the online format. The masterclasses could be

			<p>will be active. The methodological co-design workshop was divided in different parts: a co-design session during the project meeting in Rotterdam, and one-by-one online interactions with all ACTION pilots (original and those of the 1st Open Call) The data analysis workshop and the masterclasses will take place in the second half of the project.</p>			<p>implemented mostly in presence.</p>
External events	Number of events attended	50 attended external events during the project	25	22	47	31 events with talks, 7 events with poster presentations, 6 other workshops or other types of meetings, 3

						workshops at larger policy events (cf. chapters 3.9 and 3.10). Although the consortium has not fully reached the target number, the reached number can be considered a success after all, taking into account that due to the Covid-19 pandemic the number of scientific conferences was reduced. However, looking at the events in which ACTION partners participated, these ensured an important dissemination to various target groups.
Newsletters	Number of newsletters/year Number of subscribers	4 100+ per year 500 in total	3 issues	3 issues	6 issues with 782 subscribers.	Joint newsletter developed with the EU.citizen-science project and the project coordinates

						the newsletter. ACTION contributed by a subscription possibility on the ACTION website as well as articles for the newsletters (cf. chapter 3.4).
News and press releases	Number of news items/year	20+	58	118	176	The KPI was changed as the distinction between news items and non-scientific news items was difficult to identify, in particular to the citizen science activities of the projects. The 176 news items were all published on the ACTION website with related tweets and posts on social media. Disseminated through ACTION project website. They were divided by News from
	Number of press releases	10+	1	6	7	
	Number of non-scientific news items	20+				

						ACTION, News from our pilots and News on Citizen Science.
ACTION conference	Number of attendees Number of speakers	150+ participants 10+ speakers	n/a, conference will take place towards the end of the project	> 160 participants > 30 speakers > 20 virtual booths	same information as on the left	The description and evaluation of the final event can be found in chapter 3.11. The event programme and names of speakers can be found here . The registration of the whole event has been published in four videos which can be found here .
Citizen science community	Number of people reached, including all types of stakeholders, through all activities	10k			Approx. 15-20k (considering website visits, Twitter impressions, social media followers and YouTube visitors)	It is very difficult to get a correct number here, as we reached the citizen science community with most of our dissemination activities. We calculated the outreach that we

						had to the community during conferences. In addition we assumed that mainly they followed the project activities on our online channels.
Research community	Number of scientists from different disciplines reached	3k			App. 2,5k through events	The number presented here refers only to the outreach through events (talks of posters). As written in the introduction the number of participants in many events are not publicly available. So we assume that the number of scientists we reached, e.g. through social media, the website and other events was higher.

6 CONCLUSIONS

An analysis of the table above and the activities and outcomes described in the previous chapters shows that the performance of the dissemination, communication and community building activities in ACTION can be considered successful and was mostly in line with the planned target numbers. This is also confirmed by qualitative feedback from participants of the ACTION final conference. Most KPIs have been achieved by large (e.g. the number of scientific publications, the number of talks, numbers in relation to the final event, the outreach of the videos, newsletter subscribers, website visitors, etc.). Other targets were revised due to developments that were outside of the influence of the projects, mainly impacts of the Covid-19 pandemic which led to cancellations of events, change of user behaviour on social media, etc.

The highlight of the last months was the final conference which brought together an important number of players of the citizen science community. Another important achievement was the collaboration and networking with related projects, as e.g. with the EU.citizen-science project, but also with projects involved in the Horizon Results Booster “Residents Striving for Sustainable Cities” which led to new contacts and reaching new communities.

The dissemination of ACTION outputs will continue after the end of the project, mainly through the project website, but also through continued dissemination through further scientific publications and talks. A particular attention will be on the dissemination of the ACTION toolkit and the policy recommendations.

7 REFERENCES

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